

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D4.2 Digital twin resources specification document

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Lead Beneficiary: LifeWatch

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D4.2 – Digital twin resources specification document

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarizes the digital resources needed to support the scientific and technical components of the Digital Twin Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs). These resources are divided into three major types - data, analytical processes, and databases. The specifications are the result of the implementation work following the conceptual design of the DUCs provided in D4.1, “Description of demonstration use cases”. The present document provides an overview of available and missing digital resources, which must still be developed or made accessible. Thereby, the document describes the technical status of each of the eight DUCs regarding their maturity and level of integration into the Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) infrastructure. Most importantly, this document provides the technical references to guide Work Package 5 in the implementation of the DUCs within the DTO environment.

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. Introduction	7
1.1. The purpose of this document	7
1.2. From concept to implementation	7
2. DUCs.....	8
2.1. DUC 1: Invasive species management	8
2.1.1. Workflow description	8
2.1.2. Workflow diagram	8
2.1.3. Technical specifications	9
2.2. DUC 2: Impact of offshore energy infrastructures.....	13
2.2.1. Workflow description	13
2.2.2. Workflow diagram	14
2.2.3. Technical specifications	14
2.3. DUC 3: Assessment of pelagic biodiversity and human impact.....	20
2.3.1. Workflow Description	20
2.3.2. Workflow diagram	20
2.3.3. Technical specifications	21
2.4. DUC 4: Spatial planning of sustainable mariculture	22
2.4.1. Workflow description	22
2.4.2. Workflow diagram	23
2.4.3. Technical specifications	25
2.5. DUC 5: Ecosystem-based spatial planning and MPA management	37
2.5.1. Workflow description	37
2.5.2. Workflow diagram	38
2.5.3. Technical specifications	38
2.6. DUC 6: Lower-trophic level biomass monitoring to inform ocean governance.....	40
2.6.1. Workflow description	40
2.6.2. Workflow diagram	41
2.6.3. Technical specifications	41
2.7. DUC 7: Ocean Carbon Flux and Sequestration.....	43
2.7.1. Workflow description	43
2.7.2. Workflow diagram	44
2.7.3. Technical specifications	44
2.8. DUC 8: Ocean Colour/ Seasonal Sea Surface Chlorophyll-a Predictions with Neural Networks.....	48

2.8.1. Workflow description	48
2.8.2. Workflow diagram	48
2.8.3. Technical specifications	48
3. Conclusions	50
4. References	51

1. Introduction

1.1. The purpose of this document

Work package (WP) 4 will generate specific contributions to the DTO infrastructure through the Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) which are developed as analytical investigations in important fields of marine biological research, including invasive species management, offshore construction, plankton monitoring, marine aquaculture, marine protected area management, and carbon sequestration. In these areas DUCs should connect data products, applications, know-how, and expert networks in scientific narratives that showcase how digital assets can be used in the DTO. Following the conceptual design of the DUCs, we have now compiled an overview of the digital resources necessary to support these narratives. This document aspires to overview these resources in a consistent manner and thereby provide the technical specifications to WP5. These resources are divided into three major types - data, analytical processes, and databases with information on source code, availability, state of integration, interoperability, etc. In many cases, the specifications are incomplete, which means that not all DUCs have the same level of maturity. The document is intended to provide an overview of available and missing digital resources, which must still be developed or made accessible to support the DUCs. Thereby, the document describes the technical status of each DUC regarding its maturity and level of integration into the DTO. It is important however, to be aware that the DUCs are merely some examples of how data products and analytical tools can be combined in the DTO environment. The data resources provided by WP3 (and often used in the DUCs), together with the tools provided by WP5, can be combined in many ways in the future and should give rise to new DUCs as well as change existing DUCs.

1.2. From concept to implementation

The current document marks the early part of the implementation phase (Figure 1), which will gradually be accompanied by the scientific exploration and dissemination activities to end user groups towards the end of the project.

Figure 1. Timeline for design, implementation, and consolidation of DUCs.

2. DUCs

2.1. DUC 1: Invasive species management

2.1.1. Workflow description

Current approaches to detect, control, prevent, and manage marine non-indigenous species (NIS) are based on limited data and analytical insight. The workflows in this DUC aspire to support decisions by control and management agencies through provision of knowledge on early detections and recent range shifts of NIS, potential hotspots for invasions, as well as vectors and migrations routes for NIS.

The workflow in DUC 1 is based on two parts (Figure 2). Part 1 is using genetic monitoring data (metabarcoding) to detect non-indigenous species (NIS) in European coastal habitats and generate a list of target species which are new in regions of interest. Part 2 uses this list of target species to model their suitable habitat as well as distribution range under current and future climate scenarios. Together these workflows will enable investigators to quickly assess migration patterns, range shifts and invasion risks for NIS and use this knowledge to make decisions on prevention, eradication, management, and control actions.

Note, the current workflow does not produce knowledge on genetic diversity, connectivity, and migration routes for NIS, but this information is planned to be provided by a “phylogeographic module” after Part 1 and 2 are implemented.

2.1.2. Workflow diagram

Figure 2. Genetic workflow and IAS hotspot model for DUC analysis.

2.1.3. Technical specifications

Part 1 (genetic workflow)

Resource name	Sequence data
Resource type	Data
Short description	Short-read metabarcoding sequence data from ARMS MBON, EMO BON and Swedish national NIS monitoring program
Data type	Genetic data
Standard	MiXs (https://genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io/mixs/)
Format	Fastq
WP3 provided	Yes
EDITO ingestion	Need to be ingested
Volume	Medium
Example	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB72316 http://arms-mbon.github.io https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.14073

Resource name	ENA (European Nucleotide Archive)
Type	Data base
URL	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena
Short description	The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) is a repository providing free and unrestricted access to annotated DNA and RNA sequences. It also stores complementary information such as experimental procedures, details of sequence assembly and other metadata related to sequencing projects.
Relevant API(s)	API for retrieve and download records. All public records within ENA are available to retrieve from the ENA Browser API so records can be programmatically downloaded directly from the API. Associated files can be downloaded using FTP or Aspera protocol. https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/api/swagger-ui/index.html

Resource name	PEMA
Resource type	Process
Short description	PEMA is a flexible Pipeline for Environmental DNA Metabarcoding Analysis of the 16S/18S rRNA, ITS and COI marker genes. PEMA is repositied in Docker Hub as well as in Singularity Hub.
Documentation	https://hariszaf.github.io/pema_documentation/
Maturity	In production, minor updated needed during 2025
Relevant API(s)	Available through LifeWatch
HPC demand	PEMA is available through the LifeWatch VRE, incl. HPC resources
Example	https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giaa022

Resource name	Species observations
Resource type	Data
Short description	Species observation records extracted from sequence data
Data type	Species observations
Standard	DwC (https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/)
Format	csv
WP3 provided	yes
EDITO ingestion	Need to be ingested

Volume	Medium
Example	http://arms-mbon.github.io , https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.14073

Resource name	WRiMS
Type	Data base
URL	https://www.marinespecies.org/introduced/
Short description	World Register of Introduced Marine Species (WRiMS). Global database with information about introduced species, linked to World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS).
Relevant API(s)	https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu/srv/api/records/ee6b060e-3acd-48c5-9c80-16b79a86cd04

Resource name	OBIS
Type	Data base
URL	https://obis.org/
Short description	Global database and information clearing-house on marine biodiversity.
Relevant API(s)	https://api.obis.org/

Resource name	SBDI
Type	Data base
URL	www.biodiversitydata.se
Short description	Swedish Biodiversity Data infrastructure, including databases for genetic observations (http://asv-portal.biodiversitydata.se) and linked to taxonomic backbone (Dyntaxa) and national species reporting system (Artportalen). This system is used by the Swedish authorities.
Relevant API(s)	

Resource name	WRiMS checker
Resource type	Process
Short description	WRiMS invasive species checker. Provide a species list and associated sample locations and this tool will identify those species with alien status at the place of observation.
Input	Species names with geographical locations (coordinates)
Output	Species names, locations, alien status
Documentation	https://www.github.com/vliz-be-opsci/lw-iji-invasive-checker
Maturity	Script completed, available as Jupyter notebook
Relevant API(s)	unknown
HPC demand	small
Example	https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.14073

Resource name	Alien detective
Resource type	Process
Short description	Calculates the distances between a species observation and its source population through nearest known occurrences in GBIF. Is used to quantify far a species observation is from its known distribution range.
Input	Species names with geographical locations (coordinates)
Output	Plots with frequency distribution of number of known occurrences (y-axis) over distance from the observation (x-axis).
Documentation	https://github.com/IrisVP/AlienDetective

Maturity	Script is in development
Relevant API(s)	none
HPC demand	high
Example	https://github.com/IrisVP/AlienDetective/tree/main/Output_calculations

Resource name	NIS target species list and observations
Resource type	Data
Short description	Observation records of non-indigenous species (NIS) as well as their distance to potential source populations.
Data type	Species list, species observations, and images
Standard	DwC (https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/)
Format	csv and jpg/png
WP3 provided	yes
EDITO ingestion	Need to be ingested
Volume	small
Example	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-024-03503-2

Part 2 (IAS hotspot model)

Resource name	NIS target species list
Same as above	

Resource name	Draw public occurrence records (p/a)
Resource type	Process
Short description	Downloads presence and absence occurrence records from GBIF.
Input	List with non-indigenous species names
Output	Species names, locations of observation, presence/absence status
Documentation	https://github.com/biomobst/IAS_hotspot_model/tree/master
Maturity	In development
Relevant API(s)	none
HPC demand	medium
Example	https://github.com/biomobst/IAS_hotspot_model/tree/master/input%20data/Training%20points/Species%20presence%20data

Resource name	GBIF (Note, perhaps we should change this to OBIS!!!)
Type	Data base
URL	www.gbif.org
Short description	Global registry for species records and biological observations.

Resource name	Create pseudo-absence data
Resource type	Process
Short description	Provide a polygon-defined area in which the species does not occur, and the script will randomly generate absence points from this area, called "pseudo-absence points".

Input	Polygon
Output	Coordinates of absence points
Documentation	https://github.com/biomobst/IAS_hotspot_model/
Maturity	In development
Relevant API(s)	none
HPC demand	small
Example	https://github.com/biomobst/IAS_hotspot_model/tree/master/input%20data/Training%20points/Pseudabsence%20points

Resource name	Global species occurrence data for NIS
Resource type	Data
Short description	Observation records of the species in question.
Data type	Species observations
Standard	DwC (https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/)
Format	csv
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	No
Volume	small
Example	https://github.com/biomobst/IAS_hotspot_model/tree/master/input%20data/Training%20points

Resource name	Bio-oracle
Type	Data base
URL	https://www.bio-oracle.org/
Short description	Database with physical, chemical, biological and topographic data layers with global extent and uniform resolution for modelling the distribution of marine biodiversity.

Resource name	Species distribution modelling
Resource type	Process
Short description	Statistical modelling approach that predicts the distribution of a species across geographic space and time using known correlations between species presence/absence and associated environmental variables (temperatures, salinity, etc) in these locations.
Input	Species presence/absence records, environmental data layers
Output	Maps with predicted values of habitat suitability (potential distribution maps or PD maps). Test statistics. Superimposed maps with aggregated information for groups of species.
Documentation	https://github.com/biomobst/IAS_hotspot_model/
Maturity	In development
Relevant API(s)	none
HPC demand	medium
Example	https://github.com/biomobst/IAS_hotspot_model/tree/master/results

Resource name	Trend analysis Per species PD maps Per group PD maps (hotspots) Model test results (confusion matrix, ROC)
Resource type	Data

Short description	Model outputs
Data type	Maps with predicted potential distribution of NIS
Standard	GIS raster
Format	Tif, png
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	tbd
Volume	small
Example	https://github.com/biomobst/IAS_hotspot_model/tree/master/results

2.2. DUC 2: Impact of offshore energy infrastructures

2.2.1. Workflow description

The DUC is divided into three parts, representing the different data sources and methodologies. At the user side is a front end presenting an impact synthesis to aid in more ecologically informed decision-making based on multifaceted ecological indicators, related to siting offshore energy infrastructures.

Part 1. Acoustic Telemetry Data

Using acoustic telemetry data (i.e., observations of individuals at specific locations), two analytical workflows are carried out: Boosted Regression Tree (BRT) modelling (after Bangley et al., 2022), a type of encounter rate modelling, and network analysis (after Smith et al., 2024). These analyses estimate seasonal presence and migration routes, respectively. The BRT workflow uses environmental data from CMEMS and layers with Offshore Wind Farm (OWF) locations from EMODnet Human Activities.

Three map layers will be produced; a) raw observations, b) encounter rates with offshore wind farms (from the BRT workflow), and c) potential migration routes (from the network analysis workflow). To increase usability for industry and planning stakeholders, the information in the map layers will be summarized per OWF concession/Exclusive Economic Zone, and integrated into a story map (Cortes Arevalo et al., 2020) to aid decision-making.

Part 2. Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) Data

PAM data is presently available for harbor porpoise in the designated area within the European Tracking Network (ETN) data repository, concentrated in detection of porpoise positive minutes (PPM) per hour. This is not a density measure for the species, but rather a measure of detection rates. Higher click detection rates do not necessarily indicate a higher presence of porpoises in a region, as detection rates are not independent data. They simply indicate the acoustic presence of one or more porpoises during the time of detection. These data can be used to infer porpoise presence/absence in a region over time.

From the ETN, the data will be synthesized into an average PPM/hour per season metric per station. This metric will apply to a 500 m radius around the station location. The spatial planning activity will need to consider a minimum of five PAM stations per 65000 ha, which is considered the minimum number of stations sufficient for monitoring harbor porpoise presence/absence in a region (Hansen et al. 2023). In addition to these data, a map layer originating from DEPONS (<https://depons.eu/>), will provide a seasonal habitat-based average density model for harbor porpoise, primarily in the spring/summer/autumn seasons based on visual

survey data (Gilles et al., 2016). Combining visual and acoustic data, in the absence of a true density map is key to showing stakeholders how porpoises may be using an area over time.

Part 3. Ecological connectivity

This part of the DUC explicitly addresses potential disruption of ecological connectivity by offshore activity and provides relative indicators of potential connectivity impact for a set of user-provided offshore installation and will be assessed with relative metrics based on Lagrangian simulations of representative ecologically important species, based on a well-established simulation framework (Christensen et al, 2017) that is already integrated in many European research projects (e.g. MissionAtlantic, MarinePlan and CoCoNET) addressing how to include ecological connectivity in marine spatial planning and well-interfaced to sources in the DTO data lake.

2.2.2. Workflow diagram

Figure 3. Workflow diagram for Acoustic Telemetry, Passive Acoustic Monitoring, and Connectivity Analysis.

2.2.3. Technical specifications

Part 1. Acoustic telemetry data workflow

Resource type	Database
Resource name	ETN
URL	https://www.lifewatch.be/etn/
Short description	ETN database
Relevant API(s)	ETN R package (https://inbo.github.io/etn/), OpenCPU API

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Acoustic telemetry data
Short description	Acoustic telemetry data accessed via ETN.
Data type	<i>Acoustic telemetry data</i>
Standard	https://www.vliz.be/en/imis?dasid=5850&doiid=434
Format	DwC (https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/)
WP3 provided	yes
EDITO ingestion	<i>Ingested into the EDITO datalake as part of Task 3.3</i>
Volume	<i>medium</i>
Example	https://github.com/inbo/etn-occurrences , https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/charts?collection_code=ETN&advanced=1 , https://www.vliz.be/en/imis?dasid=5850&doiid=434

Resource type	Data - processed
Resource name	Raw observations layer
Short description	Acoustic telemetry data and metadata formatted for display in the map viewer.
Data type	<i>Spatiotemporal summaries of acoustic detections</i>
Standard	/
Format	<i>.csv (or any other tabular format)</i>
WP3 provided	<i>No (developed as part of DUC4.2)</i>
EDITO ingestion	/
Volume	<i>low/medium</i>
Example	https://rshiny.vsc.lifewatch.be/etn-data/?_state_id_=a0833284f334b820

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Network analysis
Short description	A network analysis is performed on the detections at various receiver locations. The result is a graph of receiver locations with metrics providing information on the connectivity between locations for a given species.
Input data	<i>Acoustic detections of individuals (timestamp, individual id, location)</i>
Output data	<i>Network graph visualizing different locations and the connections between them.</i>
Source code	https://gitlab.vliz.be/research/dto-bioflow_wp4_duc2
Maturity	<i>Not started</i>
Relevant API(s)	/
HPC demand	<i>medium</i>
Example	https://doi.org/10.1186/s40462-024-00455-z

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Per species map of migration routes

Short description	The network analysis results in a graph with nodes and weighted edges based on the calculated connectivity metrics per species. The graph needs to be converted into a format that can be used on the viewer.
Data type	<i>Point (nodes) and line (edges) geometries</i>
Standard	/
Format	<i>.geojson or .shp file</i>
WP3 provided	<i>no</i>
EDITO ingestion	/
Volume	<i>low</i>
Example	https://datavizcatalogue.com/methods/flow_map.html#google_vignette

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Boosted Regression Trees (BRT)
Short description	A BRT model will be fit to estimate the relation between an acoustic telemetry detection and specific values of different environmental covariates. This modelled relation can then be used to make predictions about the probability of encountering this species over a larger area.
Input data	<i>Acoustic detections of a species (timestamp, species, location). Environmental covariates in raster format.</i>
Output data	<i>Raster layer of predicted probabilities of encountering a species.</i>
Source code	https://gitlab.vliz.be/research/dto-bioflow_wp4_duc2
Maturity	<i>Not started</i>
Relevant API(s)	/
HPC demand	<i>medium</i>
Example	https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.851757

Resource type	Database
Resource name	EMODnet
URL	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en
Short description	EMODnet to provide environmental information (bathymetry) and socio-economic data layers (Offshore wind farm areas, shipwreck locations)
Relevant API(s)	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/emodnet-web-service-documentation , https://github.com/EMODnet/emodnet.wfs

Resource type	Database
Resource name	CMEMS
URL	Copernicus Marine Data Store Copernicus Marine Service
Short description	CMEMS to provide environmental covariates
Relevant API(s)	Copernicusmarine python package: copernicusmarine · PyPI

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Per species monthly map of encounter probability
Short description	Based on acoustic telemetry data, monthly predictions will be made on the probability of occurrence of a species.

Data type	<i>Raster maps</i>
Standard	/
Format	<i>.zarr</i>
WP3 provided	<i>No (developed as part of DUC)</i>
EDITO ingestion	/
Volume	<i>medium/large</i>
Example	/

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Map viewer
Short description	Frontend interface to data layers produced in the DUC
Data type	<i>Raster and vector layers</i>
Standard	/
Format	<i>.html</i>
WP3 provided	<i>No, but data layers developed in DUC</i>
EDITO ingestion	<i>Potentially, intermediate .zarr/.parquet files will be provided</i>
Volume	<i>medium</i>
Example	https://maps.coastalresilience.org

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Story map
Short description	Explanation of map layers, accompanied by plots and text. Means of valorisation of data layers for stakeholders.
Data type	/
Standard	/
Format	<i>.html</i>
WP3 provided	<i>No (developed in WP4 together with WP5)</i>
EDITO ingestion	/
Volume	<i>low</i>
Example	https://msp4bio.eu/belgian-part-of-the-north-sea/

Part 2. Passive Acoustic Monitoring data workflow

Resource type	Database
Resource name	ETN
URL	https://www.lifewatch.be/etn/
Short description	ETN database
Relevant API(s)	ETN R package (https://lifewatch.github.io/lwdataexplorer/)

Resource type	Data
Resource name	PAM data
Short description	Passive acoustic monitoring data as detection positive minutes per hour of harbour porpoises

Data type	<i>Passive acoustic monitoring data</i>
Standard	<i>DarwinCore</i>
Format	<i>PPM/hour</i>
WP3 provided	<i>yes</i>
EDITO ingestion	<i>Ingested into the EDITO datalake as part of Task 3.4</i>
Volume	<i>Medium</i>
Example	https://rshiny.lifewatch.be/cpod-data/

Resource type	Pre-existing model based map layer
Resource name	DEPONS
Short description	Seasonal habitat-based density model for harbour porpoise based on visual survey data, mostly collected in the summer months. Can provide minimum number of expected porpoises in an area per season.
Input data	SCANS survey data and DEPONS process-based model for assessing population effects of disturbances on marine populations.
Output data	<i>Three seasonal map layers (spring, summer, fall).</i>
Maturity	<i>Complete (Gilles et al., 2016)</i>
HPC demand	-
Example	https://depons.eu/

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Acoustic density calculation
Short description	A calculation of the detection rate per station, as in, how many minutes are positive for porpoise acoustic activity. Is not an indicator of abundance, only presence/absence.
Input data	<i>Porpoise positive minutes (PPM) per hour aggregated per season.</i>
Output data	<i>Point data shape file which contains station ID, location, and average PPM/hour per season. Metric is applicable to a 500 m radius around the station location.</i>
Maturity	<i>Not started</i>
HPC demand	<i>Low</i>
Example	

Resource type	Process
Resource name	IBM
Short description	Lagrangian 3D simulation of early life stages of different ecologically important representative fish species
Input data	<i>Dynamic hydrography from CMEMS, static habitat maps from ICES databases, user-provided potential locations of offshore installations</i>
Output data	<i>Connectivity matrices</i>
Maturity	<i>Operational</i>
HPC demand	<i>Medium / high IO</i>
Example	10.3389/fmars.2023.1141726 10.1016/j.marenvres.2016.04.004

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Impact synthesis

Short description	Interactive light weight dashboard synthesis tool that fuses output (impact indicators) from backstage processes (part 1-3 above) in visual form, based on user input
Input data	<i>User specification of offshore locations and construction details</i>
Output data	<i>Impact matrix, maps of biological distributions</i>
Maturity	<i>Not started</i>
HPC demand	<i>Low</i>
Example	

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Habitat maps
Short description	Spawning/nursery grounds for selected species
Data type	<i>boolean</i>
Standard	
Format	<i>Annotated shape, raster or filter condition (e.g. depth interval)</i>
WP3 provided	<i>no</i>
EDITO ingestion	<i>Ingested into the EDITO datalake as part of Task 3.3</i>
Volume	<i>low</i>
Example	10.1016/j.seares.2016.11.002

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Connectivity metrics
Short description	Ecological network connectivity matrix
Data type	<i>Float 2D array</i>
Standard	
Format	Netcdf or csv
WP3 provided	<i>no</i>
EDITO ingestion	<i>Ingested into the EDITO datalake as part of Task 3.3</i>
Volume	<i>low</i>
Example	os-9-261-2013

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Impact matrix
Short description	Ecological impact scoring matrix for offshore location alternatives. User scenarios in rows, ecological indicators in columns
Data type	<i>Float/integer 2D array</i>
Standard	
Format	Netcdf or csv
WP3 provided	<i>no</i>
EDITO ingestion	<i>Ingested into the EDITO datalake as part of Task 3.3</i>
Volume	<i>low</i>
Example	

2. 3. DUC 3: Assessment of pelagic biodiversity and human impact

2.3.1. Workflow Description

This DUC focuses on how large-scale assessments of plankton biodiversity patterns can be improved using a combination of new data types for a better evaluation of potential impacts on pelagic ecosystem functioning and resilience now and in the future. Furthermore, improved data streams and easy-to-use.

The workflow uses plankton abundance information. Preprocessing is required to get the data ready-to-be-used by the actual tools. Two existing tools are used to perform two separate analyses: PH1 PLET tool and PH2/3 PelHabMSFD. The tools stored their output in files (images & tables) in their associated working environment.

Migration and embedding in EDITO datablab.

- PH1 PLET tool is an Rmarkdown script and will as such be implemented. An EDITO service will be created, launching an Rstudio container with following scripts:
 - Data harvesting and preprocessing script(s)
 - The original PH1-PLET script
- PH2/3 PelHabMSFD is an R-tool with a GUI. Additional scripts for data harvesting & preprocessing are required. It is still to be decided how this will be implemented. Options range from offering the tool & scripts in an RStudio container to dockerizing the entire application.

2.3.2. Workflow diagram

Figure 4. Workflow for plankton abundance analysis using PH1 PLET & PH2/3 PelHab tool.

2.3.3. Technical specifications

The data sources are identical for both tools and both flows.

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Plankton abundance
Short description	Abundance data from imaging and genetic sources.
Data type	Abundance data from imaging and genetic sources.
Standard	<i>Provide a link to the documentation of the standard</i>
Format	PLET – example data https://github.com/hollam2/PH1_PLET_tool/tree/master/data PelHabMSFD – description https://github.com/IFREMER-LERBL/PelHabMSFD
WP3 provided	No, there is however an existing EurOBIS dataset in EDITO which will be a starting point. s3.waw3- .cloudferro.com/emodnetbiology/eurobis_occurrence_data/eurobis_occurrences_geoparquet_2024-10-01.parquet Need to follow up with WP3 to see if other suitable datasets are added.
EDITO ingestion	More data sources should be added.
Volume	Low
Example	<i>Provide a link to an example</i>

Harvesting and preprocessing scripts

The data selection & preparation are different for each tool, but their description is uniform.

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Data selection
Short description	Select geographic area (+ other data filters)
Input data	Plankton abundance
Output data	Selection
Source code	https://github.com/willem0boone/Edito_python_STAC/blob/main/Retrieve-eurobis-dataset.ipynb
Maturity	TRL5 - Ready to start building implementation
Relevant API(s)	No
HPC demand	No
Example	https://github.com/willem0boone/Edito_python_STAC/blob/main/Retrieve-eurobis-dataset.ipynb

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Data preparation
Short description	Aggregation & standardization
Input data	Selected plankton abundance
Output data	Ready to analyse data
Source code	VLIZ Gitlab - private
Maturity	TRL5 - Ready for building implementation

Relevant API(s)	No
HPC demand	No
Example	Not public

Description of tools

Resource type	Predefined process
Resource name	PH1-PLET tool
Short description	A main Rmarkdown script with supporting R scripts
Input data	Selected plankton abundance
Output data	Plots and tables
Source code	https://github.com/hollam2/PH1_PLET_tool/tree/master/R
Maturity	TRL7 - Ready implementation
Relevant API(s)	No
HPC demand	No
Example	https://github.com/hollam2/PH1_PLET_tool/tree/master/R

Resource type	Predefined process
Resource name	PH2/3-PelHabMSFD tool
Short description	Several R scripts, main script launches a GUI and runs the analysis
Input data	Selected plankton abundance
Output data	Plots and tables
Source code	https://github.com/IFREMER-LERBL/PelHabMSFD
Maturity	TRL5 - Ready for building implementation
Relevant API(s)	No
HPC demand	No
Example	https://github.com/IFREMER-LERBL/PelHabMSFD

2.4. DUC 4: Spatial planning of sustainable mariculture

2.4.1. Workflow description

Limited knowledge regarding optimal geographic placement, harvest periods, and the impact of native taxa or functional groups (e.g., predators) are challenges to the development of sustainable mariculture. This DUC integrates in situ observations, genomic data and remote sensing to develop statistical and mechanistic models for optimal mariculture planning. It innovates from traditional single-species models used for site selection by considering predation-driven production loss and estimating biomass from mariculture in various climate change scenarios. The DUC 4 workflow achieves three main goals:

- 1) Identifying suitable mariculture locations for previously defined target species.
- 2) Assessing biomass loss due to deleterious species (grazing/predation).

3) Predicting biomass yield under various climate scenarios.

Two case studies have been developed to showcase the wide applicability of our modelling approach for mariculture planning:

- 1) Portugal: kelp mariculture and grazing by fish species.
- 2) Belgium: blue mussel mariculture and predation by starfish.

Belgium’s workflow consists of two main parts: 1) development of habitat suitability model for both blue mussels (previous work by Pint et al. 2024a) and starfish throughout the year and 2) integration of this information in an existing food web model (Pint et al., 2024b) to investigate the predator-prey relationship and potential biomass loss.

2.4.2. Workflow diagram

Portugal case study

Figure 5. Workflow diagram for the Portugal case study on macroalgae modelling and biomass projections.

Belgium case study

Figure 6. Workflow diagram for the Belgium case study: Habitat suitability models and food web modelling

2.4.3. Technical specifications

Data bases used in both case studies (Portugal and Belgium)

Resource Type	Data base
Resource name	Bio-oracle
URL	https://www.bio-oracle.org/
Short description	Bio-ORACLE offers essential physical, chemical, biological and topographic data layers with global extent and uniform resolution for modelling the distribution of marine biodiversity. Database with physical, chemical, biological and topographic data layers with global extent and uniform resolution for modelling the distribution of marine biodiversity, including CMIP6 layers for projection scenarios (high resolution, ~9.2km).
Relevant API(s)	ERDDAP, manual (CMIP6)
Data Format	Asc, tif, NetCDF
EDITO ingestion	Already in the EDITO data lake
Volume	Large

Resource Type	Data base
Resource name	CMEMS
URL	https://marine.copernicus.eu/
Short description	Physical and biogeochemical database on regional and global scale, projections CMIP6 (low resolution, ~100km)
Data Format	NetCDF, csv, tiff (.tif, .geotiff)
EDITO ingestion	Already in the EDITO data lake
Volume	Large

Resource Type	Data base
Resource name	EMODnet
URL	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/
Short description	Database with physical, chemical, biological and bathymetry data layers with European extent
Data Format	NetCDF, csv, geoTIFF
EDITO ingestion	Already in the data lake
Volume	Large

Resource Type	Data base
Resource name	FishBase
URL	https://www.fishbase.org/
Short description	Global information on fish (taxonomy, biology, trophic ecology, life history, and uses, as well as historical data)
Relevant API(s)	https://fishbase.ropensci.org/

Resource Type	Data base
Resource name	SeaLifeBase

URL	https://www.sealifebase.ca/
Short description	Global database for marine species Biological and ecological information of marine species.
Relevant API(s)	https://fishbase.ropensci.org/sealifebase

Resource Type	Data base
Resource name	OBIS
URL	https://obis.org/
Short description	Ocean biodiversity database with global extent
Data type	Species occurrence (Darwincore; csv)
EDITO ingestion	It is already there
Volume	Large

Portugal study case

Resource Type	Data base
Resource name	SeaDataNet
URL	https://www.seadatanet.org/
Short description	Database with nutrients and vertical profiles of temperature, salinity and oxygen with European extent
Data Format	NetCDF, csv
EDITO ingestion	/
Volume	/

Resource Type	Data base
Resource name	GBIF
URL	https://www.gbif.org/
Short description	Global biodiversity database
Data type	Species occurrence
EDITO ingestion	/
Volume	/

Resource Type	Data base (manual review/input)
Resource name	WoRMS
URL	https://www.marinespecies.org/
Short description	Global database for marine species

Resource Type	Data base (manual review/input)
Resource name	AlgaeBase
URL	https://www.algaebase.org/
Short description	Global database of information on algae

Resource type	Data (manual review/input)
Resource name	Literature review
Short description	Literature review and expert knowledge about macroalgae and fish (herbivory)
Format	Excel document
Volume	Small

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Macroalgae model
Short description	Mechanistic modelling approach to predict potential biomass on cultivation and predation (herbivory) using physiological parameters associated to environmental variables (temperatures, salinity, irradiance, nutrients, etc).
Input	Physiological parameters and environmental data
Output	Dynamic graphics of predict values of biomass and predation
Documentation	/
Source code	/
Maturity	Work in progress
HPC demand	medium
Example	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2007.01.023 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2020.102079

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Fish model
Short description	Mono-specific modelling approach to predict biomass of fish potential predator on macroalgae cultivation
Input	Physiological parameters
Output	Dynamic graphics of predict values of biomass
Documentation	https://github.com/sizespectrum/mizer
Source code	/
Maturity	Not started
HPC demand	medium
Example	https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12256

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Spatial distribution model
Short description	Identification of the site of favourable conditions for macroalgae mariculture applying a mechanistic niche model.
Input	Physiological parameters and environmental data
Output	Dynamic graphics of predict values of biomass and predation
Documentation	/
Source code	/
Maturity	Working in progress
HPC demand	medium
Example	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2019.101529

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Macroalgae biomass predictions
Short description	Simulated macroalgae biomass production under current climate status
Data type	Model output (graphics and tables)

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Macroalgae biomass projections
Short description	Simulated projections of biomass production under different climate change scenarios.
Data type	Model output (graphics and tables), Climate scenario projections (CMIP6)
Format	Raster GeoTIFF

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Predicted habitat suitability (current situation)
Short description	Macroalgae aquaculture habitat suitability maps under current environmental status
Data type	Map of optimal areas for macroalgae aquaculture
Format	Raster GeoTIFF

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Predicted habitat suitability (future scenarios)
Short description	Macroalgae aquaculture habitat suitability maps projections under future climate scenarios
Data type	Map of optimal areas for macroalgae aquaculture under future scenarios (CMIP6)
Format	Raster GeoTIFF

Belgium case study

Part 1: Mussel-Starfish Habitat suitability model

Resource type	Multiple documents
Resource name	Literature review
Short description	Literature review and expert knowledge about blue mussels. Specific niches and preference of the blue mussel based on previous studies
Format	Word document
Volume	Small

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Fuzzy logic
Short description	Fuzzy logic is used in mechanistic modelling to integrate expert knowledge and environmental data, creating response curves that describe species-habitat relationships under varying conditions
Input data type	Literature review data, Environmental data (e.g., temperature, salinity, substrate type)
Output data type	Response curves, Habitat suitability scores
Reference	Westmeijer, G., Everaert, G., Pirllet, H., De Clerck, O., & Vandegheuchte, M. B. (2019). Mechanistic niche modelling to identify favourable growth sites of temperate macroalgae. <i>Algal Research</i> , 41, 101529. https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ALGAL.2019.101529

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Belgian EEZ Environmental data
Short description	Belgian sea environmental variables
Format	Netcdf
Volume	Large

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Response curves
Short description	Represents the relationship between species occurrence and environmental variables.
Data type	Suitability vs. temperature curve
Format	Custom csv
EDITO ingestion	It needs to be ingested into the EDITO data lake
Volume	Low

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Mechanistic modelling
Short description	Mechanistic modelling predicts species distribution by incorporating physiological constraints, environmental conditions, and species response curves derived from fuzzy logic. This approach explicitly accounts for causal relationships between organisms and their habitat.
Input Data type	Environmental data (e.g., temperature, salinity, substrate type), Occurrence data, Response curves
Output Data type	Habitat suitability maps, Predicted species distributions
Reference	Kearney, M., & Porter, W. P. (2009). Mechanistic niche modelling: Combining physiological and spatial data to predict species' ranges. <i>Ecology Letters</i> , 12(4), 334–350 Pint, S.; Moolaert, I.; Langedock, K.; Hablützel, P.; Everaert, G. (2024a). Coastbusters 2.0: Habitat suitability model. Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ): Ostend. 34 pp. https://dx.doi.org/10.48470/83

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Validation
Short description	Validation assesses the accuracy and reliability of habitat suitability models by comparing predicted distributions with independent occurrence data or known distributions.
Input Data type	Predicted habitat suitability maps, independent occurrence data, environmental data
Output Data type	Model performance metrics (AUC, TSS, Kappa), Validation plots, Error assessments
Reference	Araújo, M. B., & Guisan, A. (2006). Five (or so) challenges for species distribution modelling. <i>Journal of Biogeography</i> , 33(10), 1677–1688.,

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Aquaculture habitat suitability maps
Short description	Shows predicted suitable areas for aquaculture under current and future conditions
Data type	Map of optimal aquaculture for the blue mussel
Format	Raster GeoTIFF
EDITO ingestion	It needs to be ingested to EDITO data lake
Volume	Medium

Resource type	Data
Resource name	“What if” scenario models
Short description	Simulated projections of species distributions under different climate change scenarios to assess potential future habitat suitability.
Data type	Model output, Habitat suitability maps, Climate scenario projections
Format	Raster GeoTIFF
EDITO ingestion	It needs to be ingested into the data lake
Volume	Medium

Resource type	Data
Resource name	VLIZ eDNA
Short description	Provides biodiversity data based on environmental DNA (eDNA) sequencing for species detection and absences.
Data type	DNA-based species detections
Format	Custom csv
WP3 provided	Yes
EDITO ingestion	It needs to be ingested into the EDITO data lake
Volume	Medium

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Presence data
Short description	Observational records of starfish and mussel occurrences, providing spatial distribution information for habitat suitability modelling.
Data type	Occurrence records, Species presence-only data
Format	csv
Volume	small

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Presence-Absence data
Short description	Dataset containing presence and absence records of starfish, formatted according to Darwin Core standards.
Data type	Starfish occurrences and absences
Format	Darwin Core (csv)
EDITO ingestion	Absences data needs to be on the EDITO data lake
Volume	Large

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Forecast data
Short description	Modelled environmental variables predicting future ocean conditions under different climate scenarios derived from Bio-Oracle
Data type	Climate projections, Oceanographic variables (e.g., temperature, salinity, pH)
Format	NetCDF, GeoTIFF
EDITO ingestion	It is already on EDITO

Volume	Large
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Resource type	Process
Resource name	“What if” scenario modelling
Short description	Simulates the impact of different climate scenarios on species distribution and habitat suitability, helping to assess future risks of climate change on both the mussels and starfish.
Input Data type	Environmental data, Climate projections, Species occurrence data, Mechanistic model parameters
Output Data type	Predicted habitat suitability maps, Species distribution projections, Scenario-based risk assessments
Reference	Peterson, A. T., & Soberón, J. (2012). Species distribution modeling and ecological niche modeling: Getting the concepts right. <i>Natureza & Conservação</i> , 10(2), 102–107.

Resource type	Process
Resource name	MAXENT Modelling
Short description	Habitat suitability technique using presence-only species to estimate suitable habitat by finding the maximum entropy distribution constrained by environmental variables.
Input Data type	Presence data, Environmental variables (e.g., temperature, salinity, depth)
Output Data type	Habitat suitability maps, Response curves, Model evaluation metrics (AUC, TSS)
Reference	Phillips, S. J., Anderson, R. P., & Schapire, R. E. (2006). Maximum entropy modeling of species geographic distributions. <i>Ecological Modelling</i> , 190(3–4), 231–259

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Predator habitat suitability maps
Short description	Displays predicted distribution of marine predators based on habitat suitability models.
Data type	Map of likely starfish habitats
Standard	/
Format	Raster GeoTIFF
WP3 provided	/
EDITO ingestion	It needs to be ingested to EDITO data lake
Volume	Medium
Example	/

Resource type	Process
Resource name	GAM Modelling
Short description	Habitat suitability modelling using a statistical modelling approach that captures nonlinear relationships between species occurrence/abundance and environmental predictors using smooth functions.
Input Data type	Presence-absence or abundance data, Environmental variables (e.g., temperature, salinity, depth)
Output Data type	Habitat suitability maps, Response curves, Model evaluation metrics (AIC, Deviance Explained, RMSE)
Reference	Wood, S. N. (2017). <i>Generalized additive models: An introduction with R</i> (2nd ed.). CRC Press.

Part 2: Food web model

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Data collection for base year
Short description	Databases with information on species biomass, diets, life history and fisheries landings are downloaded and processed (excel & R studio) to retain only the information of interest. This results in several csv files.
Input data	Various data types: pdf reports and literature, csv files.
Output data	csv
Source code	/
Maturity	Ready
Relevant API(s)	/
HPC demand	No
Example	Technical report describing data collection: Pint et al. (2024c) https://dx.doi.org/10.48470/23 Datasets & R scripts: Pint et al. (2024d) https://doi.org/10.14284/668

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Life history traits
Data type	Ecological information of species (mortality, consumption-biomass ratio, production-biomass ratio, production-consumption ratio)
Standard	/
Format	Csv (data extracted manually from the Fishbase life history tool, see link: https://fishbase.mnhn.fr/popdyn/KeyfactsSummary_1.php?ID=69&GenusName=Gadus&SpeciesName=morhua&vStockCode=79&fc=183)
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	Not yet
Volume	low
Example	See 'Ecopath parameters' file in 'Data' folder: Pint et al. (2024) https://doi.org/10.14284/668

Resource type	Database
Resource name	CEFAS DAPSTOM
URL	https://www.cefasc.org.uk/data-and-publications/does/dapstom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records/
Short description	DAPSTOM (integrated database and portal for fish stomach records) is an ongoing initiative (supported by Defra and the EU) to digitize and make available fish stomach content records spanning the past 100 years. In this latest iteration (Version 6.3) an additional 26,767 records for 122,137 individual predator stomachs have been added to the dataset (including 31,488 cod stomachs), bringing the total up to 283,121 records from 481,476 stomachs and 741 distinct research cruises/sampling campaigns. Data are available for 210 predator species and a huge swathe of the Northeast Atlantic, but particularly the North Sea, Celtic Sea, Irish Sea and area around Spitzbergen. Records span the period 1836 to 2023, and the database encompasses individuals ranging in size from 0.1 cm (a herring larva) to 768 cm for a basking shark caught in 1947.
Relevant API(s)	?: https://data-api.cefasc.org.uk/index.html#/

Resource type	Data
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Resource name	Species diets
Short description	
Data type	Dietary data (matrix all species in rows and columns, values in each cell is the percentage of each species in each other's diet)
Standard	/
Format	csv
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	Not yet
Volume	low
Example	See 'diet IVc' file in 'Data' folder: Pint et al. (2024d) https://doi.org/10.14284/668

Resource type	Database
Resource name	OSPAR SCANS III
URL	https://scans3.wp.st-andrews.ac.uk/results/
Short description	Estimates of abundance for cetacean species.
Relevant API(s)	/

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Biomass
Data type	ton/km ² per species (Species biomass estimate in study area)
Standard	/
Format	csv
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	Not yet
Volume	low
Example	Technical report describing biomass data collection per species: Pint et al. (2024c) https://dx.doi.org/10.48470/23 See 'Ecopath parameters' file in 'Data' folder: Pint et al. (2024d) https://doi.org/10.14284/668

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Ecopath
Short description	All prepared files are combined to build a one-year snapshot of the food web. This process can be done in both R as well as in the Ecopath with Ecosim software. This is the basis for further food web modelling work. (https://ecopath.org/)
Input data	Csv
Output data	csv
Source code	/
Maturity	Ready
Relevant API(s)	/
HPC demand	low

Example	<p>Publication: "Food web model for the Southern Bight of the North Sea": Pint et al. (2024b) https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2024.107256</p> <p>Technical report describing the entire Ecopath process: Pint et al. (2024c) https://dx.doi.org/10.48470/23 Scripts available at: Pint et al. (2024d) https://doi.org/10.14284/668</p>
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Resource type	Process
Resource name	Data collection time series
Short description	Time series for both species biomass, as well as fisheries landings and discards in the study area are collected and processed in R to obtain a suitable format to work in the Ecopath with Ecosim software.
Input data	csv
Output data	csv
Source code	/
Maturity	Ready
Relevant API(s)	/
HPC demand	low
Example	Scripts available at: Pint et al. (2024) https://doi.org/10.14284/

Resource type	Database
Resource name	ICES fish stock assessments
URL	https://www.ices.dk/advice/Pages/adviceExplorer.aspx
Short description	Yearly reports with stock assessments for commercially important (fish) species. Only standing stock biomass (SSB) is of interest for our work.
Relevant API(s)	/

Resource type	Database
Resource name	ICES DATRAS
URL	https://www.ices.dk/data/data-portals/pages/datras.aspx
Short description	Bottom trawl surveys, for our work only catch per unit effort (CPUE) is of interest.
Relevant API(s)	https://datras.ices.dk/WebServices/Webservices.aspx

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Biomass time series
Data type	Biomass in ton/KM^2 per species per year (Based on fish stock assessments for the entire North Sea and catch per unit effort data in different areas of the North Sea, the biomass of each fish stock is calculated for our study area.)
Standard	/
Format	csv
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	Not yet
Volume	low
Example	Data available at: Pint et al. (2024) https://doi.org/10.14284/

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Environmental data time series
Data type	Average yearly sea surface temperature and salinity in study area
Standard	?
Format	csv
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	Not yet
Volume	low
Example	/

Resource type	Database
Resource name	ICES catch statistics
URL	https://www.ices.dk/data/dataset-collections/Pages/Fish-catch-and-stock-assessment.aspx
Short description	Database with historical information on fisheries landings
Relevant API(s)	/

Resource type	Database
Resource name	STECF FDI
URL	https://stecf.ec.europa.eu/data-dissemination/fdi_en
Short description	Data dissemination on EU Fisheries Dependent Information (effort, landings, discards, catches, capacity & biological information)
Relevant API(s)	/

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Data collection time series
Short description	Collection and processing of yearly biomass estimates and fisheries landings/discards (ton/km ²) information for as many species included in the food web model as possible (depending on data availability).
Input data	Yearly average (of study area) landings, discards, biomass stock assessments and environmental data time series (csv)
Output data	Csv files in appropriate format for modelling in Ecosim with Ecosim software
Source code	/
Maturity	Already done
Relevant API(s)	/
HPC demand	no
Example	Results not yet published

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Ecosim
Short description	Using the Ecosim with Ecosim model, time series data is used to fit and validate the food web model over time.
Input data	Output from the Ecosim process (previous modelling step) combined with time series for biomass, fisheries landings/discards and environmental parameters.
Output data	Biomass estimates for all species included in the model over time

Source code	https://ecopath.org/
Maturity	Already done
Relevant API(s)	/
HPC demand	medium
Example	Results not yet published

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Temporal biomass trends
Data type	Csv (ton/km ² per year)
Standard	/
Format	csv
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	No yet
Volume	low
Example	/

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Ecospace
Short description	Spatial module for food web modelling in ecopath with ecosim. Allows for spatiotemporal predictions of biomass.
Input data	Spatial habitat suitability estimates (estimated in the previously described habitat suitability models), combined with spatial data on environmental parameters and the output of the Ecosim process described above.
Output data	Maps / gridded data
Source code	/
Maturity	In progress
Relevant API(s)	/
HPC demand	medium
Example	Not yet completed

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Spatial biomass estimates
Data type	Gridded / map of biomass (ton/km ²)
Standard	/
Format	ASCII files
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	Not yet
Volume	medium
Example	https://pressbooks.bccampus.ca/ewemodel/chapter/tutorial-ecospace-maps/

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Future projections
Short description	Making predictions of suitable habitat for blue mussels and their predator-prey relationship with starfish. (using Ecopath with Ecosim software)

Input data	Bio-oracle environmental data predictions for several climate scenarios combined with the output from Ecospace (previous modelling step)
Output data	Gridded files / maps (ASCII files) of biomass (ton/km ²)
Source code	/
Maturity	Ready for implementation
Relevant API(s)	/
HPC demand	medium
Example	Not yet ready

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Spatiotemporal biomass predictions
Data type	Gridded files / maps of biomass (ton/km ²)
Standard	?
Format	(ASCII files)
WP3 provided	no
EDITO ingestion	Not yet
Volume	medium
Example	Not yet ready

2.5. DUC 5: Ecosystem-based spatial planning and MPA management

2.5.1. Workflow description

Current assessments of ecosystem service (ES) capacity are usually provided by asset-service matrices that identify the supply of ES by broad habitat type, that are not applicable to sampling and monitoring data collected at the species level. The workflows in this DUC will identify how benthic species support ecosystem service delivery and build asset-service matrices to unlock this information for monitoring and management.

Part 1. Assignment of trait values to taxa: Using OBIS and other benthic datasets, select benthic macroinvertebrate taxa for pilot study. Using existing trait databases (BIOTIC, Polytraits, Cefas Data Portal, WoRMS), link selected benthic macroinvertebrates to biological traits and identify key gaps to be addressed by review.

Part 2. Linkage of ecosystem services: Species traits linked to ecosystem services based on evidence review and expert judgement.

Part 3. Application of weighted ecosystem service contributions: Simple statistical approaches to enable users to identify and present ES capacity and its sensitivity to pressures from human activity will be explored to provide users with a tool to link sampled data to ES capacity and to map ES information.

It should be noted that due to complex contractual and financial complications work on this DUC has been delayed.

2.5.2. Workflow diagram

Figure 7. Workflow diagram

2.5.3. Technical specifications

Resource type	(Input) Data
Resource name	Polytraits
Short description	A database on biological traits of marine polychaetes, morphological, behavioural and reproductive characteristics of more than 1,000 marine polychaete species, all referenced by literature sources
Data type	Trait data (tabular)
Standard	N/A
Format	csv
WP3 provided	No
EDITO ingestion	No
Volume	
Example	

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Cefas Data Portal
Short description	Information on ten key biological traits for over a thousand marine benthic invertebrate taxa surveyed in Northwest Europe (mainly the UK shelf). Biological traits are: maximum body size, morphology, longevity, egg development location, larval development location, living habit, sediment position, feeding mode, mobility, and bioturbation mode)
Data type	Trait data (tabular)
Standard	N/A

Format	csv
WP3 provided	No
EDITO ingestion	No
Volume	
Example	

Resource type	Data
Resource name	BIOTIC/MarLIN
Short description	Database contains information on over 40 biological trait categories on approximately 680 selected benthic invertebrate species, together with additional supporting information, including a bibliography of literature from which the information was obtained.
Data type	Trait data (tabular)
Standard	N/A
Format	csv
WP3 provided	No
EDITO ingestion	No
Volume	
Example	

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Ecosystem Service List
Short description	Standardised list of Ecosystem Services
Data type	ES vocabulary
Standard	N/A
Format	csv
WP3 provided	No
EDITO ingestion	No
Volume	
Example	

Resource name	OBIS
Type	Data base
URL	https://obis.org/
Short description	Global database and information clearing-house on marine biodiversity.
Relevant API(s)	https://api.obis.org/

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Standardised Traits Architecture
Short description	List on traits and definitions collated from a range of traits databases and providers
Data type	tabular
Standard	Paper in press
Format	

WP3 provided	No
EDITO ingestion	No
Volume	Standardised Traits Architecture
Example	

Resource type	Process
Resource name	Weighted traits/ES coupling values
Short description	Expert judgement based integer (0-3) of weighted Ecosystem Service contribution values
Input Data type	<i>Trait Databases, Ecosystem Service Lists</i>
Output Data type	
Reference	

2.6. DUC 6: Lower-trophic level biomass monitoring to inform ocean governance

2.6.1. Workflow description

The goal of the DUC is to perform in-situ plankton imagery and classification for adaptive sampling in cruises of opportunity and operational contexts to assess and monitor ocean health contributing to better informed ocean governance.

Part 1: Chlorophyll a: The chlorophyll level is calculated based on satellite measurements from Copernicus service dataset on ocean color. The data is area-integrated and these measurements are supplemented with in-situ chlorophyll data, if available.

Part 2: Echosounder biomass layers: Zooplankton aggregate into visually identifiable sound scattering layers which can be detected. Standard echo metrics (Urmy et al., 2012) are calculated from the identified layers to characterise the distribution of backscatter (i.e. zooplankton).

Part 3: Particle imaging: In-situ particle imaging is used to validate whether the high levels of chlorophyll and the strong sound scattering layers are truly formed from zooplankton. Images from the camera system are analysed using a standardized pipeline in the PyOPIA toolbox, which produces particle size distributions and a basic classification of particle types (including a generic copepod class).

Part 4: Transport Model: The OpenDrift model is used to determine the transport of the zooplankton layer in the ocean. The main model inputs are vertical particle behaviour, ocean currents, and diffusivity.

2.6.2. Workflow diagram

Figure 8. Workflow diagram

2.6.3. Technical specifications

Part 1 (Chlorophyll a)

Resource name	Copernicus
Type	Data base
URL	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_BGC_L3_MY_009_113
Short description	Copernicus Marine Service
Relevant API(s)	Copernicus Marine Toolbox API

Resource name	Ocean color
Resource type	Data
Short description	Copernicus ocean colour from satellite
Data type	Satellite observations
Standard	CF
Format	Zarr
WP3 provided	No
EDITO ingestion	No
Volume	Medium
Example	https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00284

Resource name	Extract chlorophyll data for relevant region
Resource type	Process
Short description	Retrieve variables from Copernicus and integrate to region
Input	Region box coordinates, time span
Output	Time series of chlorophyll values
Documentation	Jupyter Notebook

Maturity	Under development
Relevant API(s)	None
HPC demand	None
Example	https://github.com/biomobst/IAS_hotspot_model/tree/master/input%20data/Training%20points/Species%20presence%20data

Part 2 (Echosounder biomass layers)

Resource name	Volume backscatter strength
Resource type	Data
Short description	Echosounder measurements of backscattering throughout the water column as a proxy for biological presence
Data type	Volume backscatter measurements
Standard	ICES SONAR-netCDF4 convention (https://github.com/ices-publications/SONAR-netCDF4)
Format	netCDF
WP3 provided	No
EDITO ingestion	No
Volume	Small
Example	https://oceanlabdlstorage.z6.web.core.windows.net/sig100/echo.png

Resource name	Sound scattering layer detector
Resource type	Process
Short description	Determine sound scattering layer metrics using a detection algorithm that does thresholding and mathematical morphology.
Input	Raw echograms
Output	csv file with layer metrics
Documentation	Under development
Maturity	Under development
Relevant API(s)	Under development/evaluation
HPC demand	None
Example	https://oceanlabdlstorage.z6.web.core.windows.net/sig100/echo_layer.png

Part 3 (Particle imaging)

Resource name	Particle images
Resource type	Data
Short description	In-situ camera particle images (e.g. from SilCam, LISST-HOLO, UVP)
Data type	Images
Standard	None
Format	Various (e.g. .tiff, numpy array, etc)
WP3 provided	Yes
EDITO ingestion	Processed data from PyOPIA (see process below) in agreed standard format or via EMODnet
Volume	Medium

Example	Example image from PyOPIA documentation
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Resource name	PyOPIA
Resource type	Process
Short description	Process images and produce particle size distribution and basic classification
Input	Images (e.g. from SilCam)
Output	Particle size distribution, classification information (in agreed standard format, data example under development)
Documentation	https://pyopia.readthedocs.io
Maturity	In development
Relevant API(s)	Under development/evaluation
HPC demand	None (multi-core desktop will do)
Example	https://github.com/SINTEF/pyopia/blob/main/notebooks/single-image-stats.ipynb

Part 4 (Transport model)

Resource name	OpenDrift
Resource type	Process
Short description	Calculates transport of biological particles or other materials in the ocean.
Input	Particle properties, ocean currents
Output	Particle trajectories (positions as function of time), concentrations.
Documentation	https://opendrift.github.io/index.html
Maturity	Excellent
Relevant API(s)	None, available on EDITO
HPC demand	None (can run on normal PC/laptop)
Example	https://opendrift.github.io/gallery/example_codeegg.html#sphx-glr-gallery-example-codeegg-py

Resource name	Current data
Resource type	Data
Short description	Ocean currents, measured or modelled
Data type	Data on ocean currents, as function of time and space
Standard	CF Standard
Format	netCDF
WP3 provided	No
EDITO ingestion	No
Volume	Small to medium
Example	https://thredds.met.no/thredds/catalog/fou-hi/norkyst800m-1h/catalog.html

2.7. DUC 7: Ocean Carbon Flux and Sequestration

2.7.1. Workflow description

Global carbon flux estimates face significant uncertainties due to observational gaps and insufficient modeling of particle processes. This DUC aims to improve carbon export models by integrating sparse but

highly characterized particle data from the Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP) and bio-optical sensors with continuous remote sensing data for more accurate global flux estimates.

Two sub-use cases are identified: (1) estimating carbon flux from UVP-derived particle size distributions (PSDs) and (2) assessing flux in calcifying phytoplankton blooms using bio-optical data.

For **use case 1**, PSDs from a global UVP dataset are first fit to a polynomial function, extracting three key parameters. An XGBoost model then correlates these parameters with surface environmental data to upscale PSDs globally. The relationship between PSDs and a global carbon flux benchmarking database is then used to derive large-scale carbon flux estimates, available at weekly and 1 degree resolution, with annual updates.

Use case 2 focuses on BGC-Argo floats sampling calcifying phytoplankton blooms. By analyzing bio-optical and physical measurements from these floats, carbon flux properties of calcifying blooms will be compared with other phytoplankton blooms, demonstrated in the North Atlantic. This will clarify the role of calcifying phytoplankton in global carbon export.

2.7.2. Workflow diagram

Figure 9. Workflow diagram

2.7.3. Technical specifications

Use Case 1:

Resource name	Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP) data
Resource type	Data

Short description	Particle size distribution data from UVPs deployed on different platforms (rosettes, gliders, BGC-Argo floats, moorings, etc.)
Data type	Imaging data
Standard	N/A
Format	NetCDF (Argo format)
WP3 provided	Yes
EDITO ingestion	Need to be ingested
Volume	~30k vertical profiles
Example	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.934090

Resource name	EcoPart
Type	Data base
URL	https://ecopart.obs-vlfr.fr/
Short description	EcoPart is a repository built specifically to store and distribute UVP data, although it can also store similarly formatted data (e.g., LISST, CPICS). EcoPart structures its information by size and exports depth-resolved particle size spectra. EcoPart currently hosts ~30k public UVP profiles, recording size spectra of particulate matter from 0.01 to 2.5 cm.
Relevant API(s)	An API to retrieve and download records from EcoPart is under development. All public UVP profiles will be available for export as NetCDF files. https://github.com/ecotaxa/ecopart back

Resource name	PSD log-quadratic fitting
Resource type	Process
Short description	Fits a log-quadratic modified Junge's law to each particle size distribution to extract the coefficients. These coefficients can then be used to link PSD data to environmental data known for their influence on marine biogeochemical processes.
Documentation	Scientific publication in progress (Ranini et al. 2025)
Maturity	Implemented
Relevant API(s)	N/A
HPC demand	None for now
Example	To be published

Resource name	Environmental data
Resource type	Data
Short description	Environmental data that may play a role in PSD variations, including GEMCO Bathymetry data, World Ocean Atlas climatologies for BGC-relevant variables, Copernicus Ocean Colour derived data, Copernicus Sea Surface Temperature data, and Copernicus Nemo model data products. Use Case 2 uses the Ocean colour satellite product for the concentration of Particulate Inorganic Carbon (PIC) to identify blooms of calcifying phytoplankton.

Data type	Environmental data and data products; Mission-Merged Level3 Ocean Colour products (Gridded data)
Standard	N/A
Format	NetCDF
WP3 provided	Yes (data sources or equivalents should all be in the DTO data lake)
EDITO ingestion	Ingested
Volume	Medium
Example	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L4_MY_009_104/description ; https://www.gebco.net/data_and_products/gridded_bathymetry_data/gebco_2023/ ; https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JC002378 ; https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/world-ocean-atlas ; https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00281 ; https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00168 ; https://hermes.acri.fr/index.php?class=archive

Resource name	PSD XGBoost model
Resource type	Process
Short description	Uses XGBoost to predict the three quad-log coefficients globally using the environmental data.
Documentation	Scientific publication in progress (Ranini et al. 2025)
Maturity	Implemented
Relevant API(s)	N/A
HPC demand	small, currently provided locally
Example	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1603.02754

Resource name	Model carbon flux from PSD
Resource type	Process
Short description	Models vertical carbon flux based on particle size and distribution. Flux is expressed over a specific size range of particles as a function of the abundance, the settling velocity and the carbon content of marine snow, three functions that are assumed to be size driven.
Documentation	Scientific publication in progress (Ranini et al. 2025)
Maturity	Implemented
Relevant API(s)	N/A
HPC demand	None for now
Example	Alldredge et al. (1988) , Guidi et al. (2008) , Iversen et al. (2010)

Resource name	Global Particulate Organic Carbon (POC) database
Type	Data base
URL	Under construction

Short description	A regularly updated global POC database, integrating observations from in situ optical measurements, sediment traps, model products, satellite observations, CTD/rosettes, Thorium/Uranium deficit measurements, etc.
Relevant API(s)	N/A
Format	NetCDF, GIS, Ocean Data View
WP3 provided	No; database will be maintained outside of the DTO

Resource name	Maps of carbon flux
Resource type	Data
Short description	Model outputs
Data type	Maps with global carbon flux at weekly and 1° resolution, updated annually
Standard	N/A
Format	GIS?
WP3 provided	No
EDITO ingestion	Not yet ready
Volume	TBD
Example	Not yet generated

Use Case 2:

Resource name	BioGeoChemical-Argo DAC
Resource type	Data base
Short description	Vertical profiles from the surface to 1000m depth of Temperature, salinity, chlorophyll-a fluorescence (Fchl) and particle backscattering at 700 nm (bbp). Particle data from UVP6s deployed on Argo floats will be recuperated from the Argo DAC for import in EcoPart and the DTO.
Data type	Vertical profiles, delayed mode data quality
Format	NetCDF (Argo format)
Example	https://www.coriolis.eu.org/Observing-the-Ocean/ARGO

Resource name	Match ups between ocean color satellite data and BioGeoChemical-Argo data for floats in North Atlantic Ocean
Resource type	Process
Short description	Matching in time and space of satellite-derived PIC and BGC-Argo vertical profiles
Documentation	Scientific publication in progress (Rasse and Neukermans)
Maturity	Implemented
Relevant API(s)	N/A
HPC demand	N/A
Example	Terrats et al. 2020

Resource name	Particle fluxes from bio-optical measurements on BGC-Argo floats in the North Atlantic
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Resource type	Process
Short description	Fluxes and stocks of particles, calculated from particle backscattering (b_{bp})
Documentation	Scientific publication in progress (Rasse and Neukermans)
Maturity	Implemented
Relevant API(s)	N/A
HPC demand	N/A
Example	Dall’Olmo & Mork 2014; Briggs et al. 2020

Resource name	Carbon flux in the North Atlantic associated with blooms of calcifying phytoplankton
Resource type	Data
Short description	Outputs of the processes
Data type	Figures and maps showing particle fluxes associated with blooms of calcifying phytoplankton in the North Atlantic
Standard	N/A
Format	Png, csv
WP3 provided	N/A
EDITO ingestion	tbd
Volume	N/A
Example	N/A

2.8. DUC 8: Ocean Colour/ Seasonal Sea Surface Chlorophyll-a Predictions with Neural Networks

2.8.1. Workflow description

Accurate seasonal chlorophyll-a forecasting, even if limited to the surface level, can have a variety of important applications (biodiversity conservation, fisheries management, algal bloom detection, etc.). Traditionally, this is done using biogeochemical models, which are based on differential equations that model nutrient and carbon cycles, but these can be computationally prohibitive and difficult to parametrize.

Using machine learning, we estimate chlorophyll-a from physical variables, and by using publicly available forecasts of these variables as input, we can generate an ensemble of seasonal chlorophyll-a predictions.

2.8.2. Workflow diagram

Figure 10. Workflow diagram

2.8.3. Technical specifications

Resource type	Data
Resource name	Seasonal monthly forecast averages of ocean variables (MLD, SSH, SSS), Seasonal monthly statistics on single levels (SST)

Short description	Forecasts of MLD, SSH, SSS and SST, used as input for the neural network
Data type	<i>Forecast</i>
Standard	
Format	<i>NetCDF</i>
WP3 provided	<i>No (the data is publicly available)</i>
EDITO ingestion	<i>As temporary files (for preprocessing and forecast generation)</i>
Volume	
Example	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/seasonal-monthly-single-levels?tab=overview https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/seasonal-monthly-ocean?tab=overview

Resource type	Database (Input data for the model)
Resource name	Seasonal forecast of ocean variables (same as above)
URL	https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/seasonal-monthly-single-levels?tab=overview https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/seasonal-monthly-ocean?tab=overview
Short description	Seasonal forecast of ocean variables (same as above)
Relevant API(s)	CSDAPI https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/how-to-api

Resource type	(Output) Data
Resource name	Seasonal Chl-a forecast (output data)
Short description	
Data type	<i>Chl-a Forecast</i>
Standard	NA
Format	<i>NetCDF</i>
WP3 provided	NA
EDITO ingestion	<i>Yes, to be overwritten each month with the newest forecast and available for viewing / downloading</i>
Volume	N/A
Example	NA

Resource type	Process(es)
Resource name	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Download the MLD, SSH, SSS, SST forecasts from the CDS (using API) 2. Preprocess data 3. Generate prediction using the machine learning model
Short description	
Input data	MLD, SSH, SSS, SST forecasts (see above)
Output data	Chl-a forecast (see above)
Source code	Will publish once the paper is accepted
Maturity	Working on creating the Docker container for integration as a process (https://pub.pages.mercator-ocean.fr/edito-infra/edito-tutorials-content/#/Contribution/process-playground)

Relevant API(s)	N/A
HPC demand	Medium
Example	N/A

3. Conclusions

This deliverable outlines a detailed specification of the digital resources required for the implementation of the DUCs within the DTO-BioFlow project. Through interdisciplinary collaboration and the integration of diverse data and analytical processes, significant progress has been made towards establishing an oceanic digital twin that can effectively support marine biodiversity management and monitoring for these use cases.

Key resources, including data, analytical processes, and databases, have been identified and specified, providing a solid foundation for future implementations and developments within the project.

Each DUC demonstrates how the combination of data products and analytical tools can be used to enhance understanding and management of marine systems.

Challenges regarding resources that still need to be developed or made accessible are acknowledged. However, the document outlines plans to address these gaps, ensuring that the DUCs will integrate those resources.

This deliverable not only reflects the current state of the DTO BioFlow project's resources but also establishes a clear path for future expansion and refinement of the digital twins.

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